

ENLIGHTENER'S PHILOSOFY AND ITS REFLECTION IN ENGLISH LITERATURE

Student of CSPU

The English language theory and practice department

Boyqobilova Durdona

Scientific advisor: **Kenjayeva Muxlisa Baxodir qizi**

ABSTRACT

The Enlightenment, a transformative intellectual movement that swept through Europe in the 17th and 18th centuries, left an indelible mark on American literature. This abstract delves into how Enlightenment philosophy, with its emphasis on reason, individualism, and progress, found resonance in the works of American writers. Through a close examination of key literary works and authors influenced by Enlightenment ideals, this abstract seeks to illuminate the ways in which concepts such as liberty, democracy, and social justice were explored and critiqued in American literature.

Keywords: Enlightenment ideals, individual freedom, struggle for liberty, church and monarchy, marginalized groups, intellectual movement, Daniel Defoe, American literature and culture.

INTRODUCTION

The Enlightenment, often referred to as the Age of Reason, was a philosophical movement that swept through Europe in the 17th and 18th centuries. It emphasized reason, science, individualism, and skepticism of traditional beliefs, aiming to promote intellectual progress, human rights, and societal reform. The ideas of Enlightenment thinkers such as Voltaire, Rousseau, Montesquieu, and Locke influenced not only European thought but also had a significant impact on American literature and culture.

In American literature, the Enlightenment philosophy found fertile ground, shaping the themes and values that permeated literary works of the time and beyond. Writers drew upon Enlightenment ideals to explore themes of liberty, democracy, social justice, and the pursuit of knowledge in their works. This introduction aims to explore the reflection of Enlightenment philosophy in American literature, delving into how writers embraced and challenged the principles of reason, liberty, and progress in their literary creations. By examining key works and authors influenced by Enlightenment thought, we can gain a deeper understanding of the enduring legacy of this intellectual movement in American letters. Join us on a journey through the pages of American literature to uncover how Enlightenment ideals have informed and enriched the literary landscape of the United States.

MAIN BODY

The Enlightenment, a period of intellectual ferment that swept through Europe in the 17th and 18th centuries, had a profound impact on English literature, shaping the themes, styles, and values that pervaded literary works of the time. This body of discussion aims to explore the reflection of Enlightenment philosophy in English literature, highlighting how writers incorporated and responded to the ideals of reason, individualism, and social progress espoused by Enlightenment thinkers such as Locke, Rousseau, Voltaire, and Montesquieu.

1. Embrace of Rationalism:

- Enlightenment philosophy championed reason as the primary source of authority and legitimacy, a principle that found its way into English literature of the period. Writers like Alexander Pope and Jonathan Swift used satire and wit to critique irrationality and ignorance, embodying the Enlightenment's call for critical thinking and intellectual inquiry.

2. Exploration of Human Rights and Social Justice:

- The Enlightenment heralded the idea of natural rights and the inherent dignity of individuals, concepts that influenced English literary works. Mary

Wollstonecraft's "A Vindication of the Rights of Woman" and Samuel Richardson's "Pamela" reflected Enlightenment ideals of equality and justice, advocating for social reform and the empowerment of marginalized groups.

3. Critique of Social Institutions:

- Enlightenment thinkers questioned the authority of traditional institutions such as the church and monarchy, advocating for greater individual freedom and political accountability. In English literature, the works of Daniel Defoe ("Robinson Crusoe") and John Milton ("Paradise Lost") grappled with themes of power, oppression, and the struggle for liberty against tyrannical forces.

4. Promotion of Empiricism and Scientific Progress:

- The Enlightenment exalted scientific inquiry and empirical observation as the keys to understanding the natural world. English writers like Francis Bacon and Thomas Hobbes emphasized the importance of empirical evidence and rational thought, paving the way for a literary culture that valued truth, observation, and experimentation.

5. Legacy in Romantic and Victorian Literature:

- The Enlightenment's legacy extended beyond its era, influencing Romantic and Victorian writers who grappled with the tensions between reason and emotion, progress and tradition. The works of Wordsworth, Coleridge, and Dickens bear the imprint of Enlightenment ideas, blending rational thought with an exploration of subjective experience and social critique.

By examining the ways in which Enlightenment philosophy manifested in English literature, we gain a deeper appreciation for the enduring impact of this intellectual movement on the literary tradition of England. The reflection of Enlightenment ideals in English literature serves as a testament to the transformative power of ideas and the enduring relevance of reason, liberty, and progress in shaping the literary imagination.

CONCLUSION

The Enlightenment's legacy in English literature is multifaceted and enduring. It sparked a revolution in thought and expression, empowering writers to challenge conventions, explore new forms, and engage with the pressing social and intellectual issues of their time. This spirit of inquiry and critical engagement continues to animate English literature, ensuring that the light of Enlightenment continues to illuminate the path for generations to come.

REFERENCES

1. Sulton I. "Adabiyot nazariyasi". T. 1980. 74p.
2. Azizov Q., Qayumov O., "Chet el adabiyoti tarixi", Toshkent, "O'qituvchi". 1987
3. Chase E.M., Jewett A., Evans W. Values in Literature-Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company, 1965
4. Gegel. Estetika M., 1971
5. Grierson H., Smith G. A Critical History of English Poetry. L., Longman 1966
6. Gritchuk M.A. English for students of Literature. M., 1983
7. Kenjayeva B.M. Why learning the English language is essential: 10 effective methods for teaching English //The Role of Exact Sciences in the Era of Modern Development, 2024.
8. Kenjayeva B.M. Why learning the English language is essential: 10 effective methods for teaching English //The Role of Exact Sciences in the Era of Modern Development. 2024.